

Advancing Capacity and analytical Tools for supporting Common Agricultural Policies post 2027

D1.1: An operational food systems framework for analysing sustainable food systems outcomes

Subtitle if needed

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APPROVED BY WP MANAGER:	Hans van Meijl (WR)
DATE OF APPROVAL:	01.05.2025
APPROVED BY PROJECT COORDINATOR:	Hans van Meijl (WR)
DATE OF APPROVAL:	01.05.2025
Topic ID	Advancing Capacity and analytical Tools for supporting Commission Agricultural Policies post 2027
WORK PROGRAMME CALL	HORIZON-CL6-2023-GOVERNANCE-01 Innovative governance, environmental observations and digital solutions in support of the Green Deal
PROJECT WEB SITE:	https://act4cap27.eu/

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History of changes

Version	Publication date	Changes	Who
V01	May-July 2024	Initializing the document	Siemen van Berkum
V02	November 2024- March 2025	Further elaboration of the document	Siemen van Berkum, Saeed Moghayer
	April 2025	Review	Verena Laquai, Karen Arcia, Hans van Meijl
V03	April 2025	Feedback processed	Saeed Moghayer, Siemen van Berkum
V04	May 2025	Approved	Hans van Meijl
V05	January 2026	Updated after the review	Siemen van Berkum

Citation

Siemen van Berkum (WR), Saeed Moghayer (WR), Verena Laquai (Thuenen and Karen Arcia (Thuenen (2025)). Deliverable D1.1. An operational food systems framework for analysing sustainable food systems outcomes. ACT4CAP27 Horizon Europe project GA Nr. 10113487.

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Abbreviations / Definitions

CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CBAM	Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism
CO2	carbon dioxide
COMEXT	Eurostat reference for international trade in goods
DG AGRI	Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development
EGD	European Green Deal
F2F	Farm to Fork
FADN	Farm Accountancy Data Network
FSA	food system approach
HLPE-FSN	High Level Panel of Experts on Food Security and Nutrition of the Committee on World Food Security
iMAP	Integrated Modelling Platform for Agro-economic, Commodity and Policy Analysis
JRC	Joint Reserach Centre – European Commission
NPK	nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents a comprehensive framework for assessing sustainable food system outcomes in the context of EU policies, particularly the European Green Deal (EGD) and the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). Complex relationships between food system (external) drivers, activities (from input supplier to consumer) and outcomes (in terms of food security, economic, social and environmental effects) are concisely explained and the way in which food system actors and markets interact at multiple levels is described. The analytical framework developed within the ACT4CAP27 project provides a structured methodology to evaluate policy impacts on multiple food system outcomes, ensuring that interventions align with long-term sustainability goals.

Food systems are shaped by a wide range of drivers, including economic market dynamics, technological advancements, social and institutional factors, and biophysical conditions. A key message of this report is that the interactions between these drivers and food system activities generate trade-offs and synergies between different societal challenges that must be carefully considered in policy design. While the EGD and implementing strategies introduce ambitious targets for sustainability, their implementation requires integrated policy approaches that account for the economic viability of food system actors, the resilience of supply chains, and the accessibility of nutritious diets for all consumers.

Furthermore, our analysis highlights the importance of robust indicators to monitor and evaluate food system performance. The recent development of the EU Food System Dashboard by the Joint Research Centre (JRC) and the Interactive CAP Indicator dashboard offers valuable monitoring frameworks for tracking progress across various sustainability dimensions. However, the current state of data availability and modelling capacities still presents limitations in capturing the full scope of food system transformations. For example, the impacts of input reductions on productivity at farm level or on the environment (e.g. biodiversity and water quality) are still not sufficiently captured, and models provide still too little insight into the consequences of interventions for the food processing industry and consumers (e.g. in terms of food access). In the ACT4CAP27 project we seek to address these gaps by refining existing modelling tools and incorporating a broader set of indicators to assess the impacts of future agriculture policies on EU's food system in the first place, but also to address comprehensively (other) components of the Green Deal.

PRELUDE

The call for proposals to which the ACT4CAP27 consortium successfully responded¹ set the condition that the awarded project should cooperate with other Horizon Europe-funded projects. In the implementation of ACT4CAP27, complementarity with previously funded projects and currently ongoing projects is ensured by the fact that the partners involved in ACT4CAP27 almost all belong to the core of the institutes working on quantitative policy models (iMAP, other links). ACT4CAP27 has a strong connection with BrightSpace and Lamasus which are also HEU financed projects in which modelling tools are improved for agricultural policy evaluation. With these two projects, ACT4CAP27 is developing a white paper² on the economic and societal importance of agriculture in the EU and the contribution of quantitative modeling to policy design and evaluation; in addition, both projects jointly develop a baseline projection (a future with continuation of currently known policies) for the agricultural and food market in the EU.

The connection with BrightSpace is even somewhat stronger in that both projects (ACT4CAP27 and BrightSpace) take the principle goals of the EU Green Deal (EGD) as a starting point and analyse policies that should contribute to the Green Deal's objectives in an integrated way. The latter means evaluating policies for their social, economic and environmental impacts and in relation to each other. BrightSpace arrives at a framework of analysis for policy by defining the concepts of a safe and just space (Raworth, 2012;2017) and from these indicating thresholds of that space in socio-economic and ecological dimensions. The ACT4CAP27 project looks at the effects of policies through a food system lens and, in doing so, at the social, economic and environmental performance of the whole food system.

As a result, the conceptual analytical framework of both projects has similarities. After all, both projects improve the model toolbox to conduct integrated policy evaluations and focus particularly on the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and EGD policies relevant to the agriculture and food sector. At the same time, there are differences. Whereas BrightSpace focuses on policy implication for EU farmers mainly and on impacts of existing agricultural policies (that is, the CAP as it is defined for 2023-2027 period), the ACT4CAP27 project applies a food system approach in analysing policy impacts, what implies including all food supply chain actors including food consumers as subject of policy impact assessments, and the project will focus on future (that is post-2027) agricultural policies.

Due to the fact that ACT4CAP27 focuses more broadly on all actors in the food system and on future policy goals and instruments (but this is subject to proposals from the EC in the near future), different model innovations will be worked on in ACT4CAP27 than in BrightSpace. It is also likely that ACT4CAP27 will have to anticipate different policy goals and/or policy instruments compared to BrightSpace. This most likely will imply that the evaluation tools need to have an (even) broader set of impact indicators than is being developed in BrightSpace. Nevertheless, it is also obvious that ACT4CAP27 builds strongly on the knowledge, data collection and model innovations built in BrightSpace and other HEU funded research projects.

¹ HORIZON-CL6-2023-GOVERNANCE-01-2: Advancing analytical capacity and tools to support EU agri-food policies post 2027

² Sustainable agricultural sector: A key component of EU economic recovery and security: A science-based perspective.

1. INTRODUCTION: CONTEXT AND WHY WE NEED A FOOD SYSTEM APPROACH

1.1. Greater emphasis on sustainability in European policies

The European Green Deal (EGD), launched in December 2019 by the European Commission (EC), aims, among others, to increase the contribution of the European Union (EU) agriculture to climate change action, improve the management of natural resources, ensure a fair economic return for farmers, and reinforce the protection of biodiversity (EC, 2019). Targets to be met in 2030 are further specified in the Farm to Fork (F2F) Strategy that is designed to ‘accelerate the transition to a fair and, healthy and environmental-friendly food system’ (EC, 2020a). More specifically, the F2F strategy aims to a sustainable food system that should: 1) have a neutral or positive environmental impact; 2) help to mitigate climate change and adapt to its impacts; 3) reverse the loss of biodiversity; 4) ensure food security, nutrition and public health, making sure that everyone has access to sufficient, safe, nutritious, sustainable food, and 5) preserve affordability of food while generating fairer economic returns, fostering competitiveness of the EU supply sector and promoting fair trade (ibid footnote 1). In presenting its objectives the EC suggests the F2F strategy impacts all parts of the food supply chain including the consumer (see figure 1.1). The strategy sets out both regulatory and non-regulatory initiatives, with the common agricultural and fisheries policies as key tools to support a just transition of EU’s agriculture and food system.

Figure 1.1 Farm to Fork Strategy includes the sustainability of all components of EU’s food system

EU agriculture and food practices are currently not on the right track to meet the EGD ambitions and objectives (e.g. Guyomard, Bureau et al., 2020; EC, 2020; IEEP, 2024). These objectives are interdependent, and while often aligned, they may also compete. After all, the need to restore biodiversity and soil health will have to be accompanied by extensive production methods that may generate lower yields, which can reduce the farmer’s income. Moreover, a transition to a food system that improves access to (more) healthy, nutritious food may mean that the actors in the food chain will have to produce other products, which may cause resistance because this will be accompanied by possible loss of market positions and, in any case transaction costs for actors who want to adapt to a new situation. The potential synergies and trade-offs of impacts of policy

interventions for economic, social (including health), environmental and climate change induced outcomes of a food system need to be well understood in order to arrive at the policy mix that does justice to the societal aspirations.

1.2. Farm-to-Fork: Challenges and Continued Influence on Future Agricultural Policy

These societal aspirations have changed significantly in recent years. Soon after the F2F was published in 2020, strong farmer protests arose in a series of EU Member States against environmental requirements that were considered too stringent, putting pressure on the profitability of farming and causing 'unfair competition' with foreign supply that did not have to comply with similar rules. International market disruptions caused by the COVID pandemic in 2020 and 2021, and the Russian-Ukrainian conflict - which in the early months of 2022 pushed up international energy and food prices - led to growing public concern about the fragile state of food security in the EU, also because the proposed European policy adjustments resulting from the EGD could lead to lower agricultural production in the EU (e.g. Beckman et al., 2023; Bremmer et al., 2021). All in all, political unease gradually grew against the ambitious environmental and climate neutral targets as included in the F2F (Aubert, 2023). This led to the European Commission implementing various relaxations in regulations, including the ways in which farmers can rotate and diversify crops and the reduction targets of crop pesticide use. In order to ensure greater support for an agricultural transition, the EC proposed a Strategic Dialogue (announced by President Von der Leyen in the State of the Union 2023) in which a very broad group of stakeholders discussed the future of the agricultural sector and food systems in the EU. The Dialogue resulted in fourteen recommendations, including that an adjustment of the European Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) should meet three objectives: providing socio-economic support to farmers; promoting positive environmental, social and animal welfare outcomes; and strengthening the framework conditions for rural areas (Strategic Dialogue, 2024). The Strategic Dialogue report is a collective call for change, stating clearly that "business-as-usual is not an option", but also expresses the desire for a better balance between the need for sustainability and economic growth.

The F2F strategy as an overarching policy framework for the agri-food sector has therefore become more into the background with the European Commission taking office in December 2024. Agriculture Commissioner Hansen's Vision document, presented in February 2025, places more emphasis on strengthening the competitive position of the agricultural sector and the earning capacity of current and new generations of farmers (EC, 2025). At the same time, the Vision paper makes clear to strive for a "future-proof agri-food sector that is functioning within planetary boundaries, where farming and the food sector contribute together to the EU's climate objectives, while preserving healthy soils, clean water and air, and protecting and restoring Europe's biodiversity" (p.5). With these statements, the Vision document still endorses the objectives of the EGD, but places more emphasis on competitiveness and the socio-economic objectives; with this direction, DG AGRI's Vision document indicates that it wants to better balance the previous emphasis on the green dimension with social and economic objectives. The EC also emphasises that it wants to work towards "a resilient and sustainable agrifood system" (EC, 2025:9) and that agricultural policy should be evaluated in the broader context of the food system performance. This is in line with the F2F-strategy in which the pursuit of a sustainable food system is a key objective. The F2F strategy document may no longer play a prominent role in the discussion on the future of the CAP, but the objectives of F2F still seem to resonate so much with

the Vision document that we find sufficient justification there to consider the F2F objectives as starting points for our project.

To accelerate the transition to sustainable food systems in the EU, there is an urgent need to significantly change agri-food policies post 2027 and the future EU legal framework for sustainable food systems in line with EU policy objectives, for example by retargeting direct payments, adapting technical provisions of the CAP (e.g. direct payments conditionality requirements and eco-scheme measures) and enhance CAP governance (legally binding, enforcement). Agricultural policies need to be better embedded in the broader picture of food systems in the bioeconomy, including interventions focusing on consumer behavioural change, food diets, public health, and the circular economy.

1.3. Implications for quantitative research to support policy evaluation

Policy makers and opinion leaders, however, often lack sufficient information to gauge the likely effects of a food system crises on their country. They thus miss the opportunity to identify, design, and implement policy actions that can best avoid short- and long-term risk and use opportunities. Insufficient information and understanding of interrelationships can lead to over- and under reactions, resulting in policy and market failures.

However, also the current model toolbox that is widely applied in ex-ante EU agricultural policy analyses all have their limitations to study the impact of agri-food policies post 2027 on EU's food systems outcomes; they often focus on the primary agricultural sector and little on the food supply chain. Moreover, they lack depth and scope to analyse key elements of a sustainability-promoting future agricultural policy such as the introduction of carbon farming schemes, promotion of increased biodiversity in agricultural landscapes, and incentives for innovation and circular economy, and to estimate policy impacts on food related consumer behaviour and public health. The ACT4CAP27 project is a collective effort by the AGMEMOD, CAPRI, GLOBIOM and MAGNET modelling teams to work together on these challenges by adapting their models to allow for broader considerations of policy objectives and to gain and share insights into how proposed policies impact EU's food systems economically, socially and environmentally.

1.4. Aim and structure of the paper

This paper's aim is to define an overall conceptual framework of EU food systems for the identification of drivers, performance indicators and gaps in modelling tools to assess policy impacts. To this end, it answers two questions; what is a structured, feasible methodology to evaluate policy impacts on multiple food system outcomes, and what are appropriate indicators to measure sustainability of the EU food systems. The proposed conceptual framework clarifies how food system activities are related to food system outcomes. This will help to design model improvements and improved links between the quantitative tools for contributions to better policy analysis, considering the food system perspective. Unlike previous approaches that often focus on individual components of the food system in isolation (e.g., agricultural production or consumer behaviour), our framework provides a more holistic perspective.

The structure of the paper is as follows. Section 2 briefly describes different ways of conceptualising food systems, followed by a definition of the conceptual framework to be used in ACT4CAP27 and a description of the foundations of the ACT4CAP27 conceptual framework, including a picture of food system activities and the drivers that shape the system. The section

concludes by indicating the usefulness of the approach for policy analyses (i.e. monitoring and evaluation of policy interventions). Section 3 elaborates on the societal goals that a food system should deliver: to produce sufficient and healthy food that is produced sustainably and that enables food chain actors to achieve a good livelihood. Food system performance should be measured in order to monitor and evaluate the extent to which food systems achieve societal goals. Section 3 also presents some frameworks designed to evaluate performance of the EU food system, providing insights into the indicators and data these frameworks apply. In Section 4 we confront our food system framework with the European public policy goals as formulated in the EGD and the CAP. By linking them, we show which food system outcomes the policy is aimed at and what an evaluation of the policy results, including the associated indicators, should focus on. In Chapter 5, we discuss two so-called dashboards that have already been developed to measure the (un)sustainable state of the EU food system. These dashboards provide a rich overview of indicators and associated data sources that can be used to monitor and evaluate the impact of policy on economic, social and environmental sustainability. The dashboards are therefore a source of inspiration for our next step in the project to decide which indicators (and data) should be included in our models to be able to monitor and evaluate the impact of agri-food policies post 2027 on the EU food systems. Section 6 concludes with summarising concluding remarks.

2. A FRAMEWORK TO ASSESS SUSTAINABLE FOOD SYSTEM OUTCOMES: THE ACT4CAP27 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This chapter provides a brief review of how food systems are conceptualised and sustainable food systems are defined. It also highlights the usefulness of a food systems approach for policy analyses aimed at making a food system more sustainable. Section 2.1 outlines the components of a food system and the relationships between them, and proposes a conceptual framework to map a food system and the relationships between drivers, actors, activities and outcomes in a food system. Section 2.2 elaborates on the drivers of food system change, exogenous factors that consistently over a period of time influence the activities and outcomes of a food system. In Section 2.3 we highlight the importance of setting boundaries of a food system and Section 2.4 emphasizes the usefulness of systems thinking in finding ways towards sustainable food systems.

2.1. A food system definition and conceptualisation

Food systems are complex entities comprising all the processes associated with food production and food utilisation, such as growing, harvesting, packing, processing, transporting, marketing, consuming and disposing of food remains. All these activities require natural resources and other (human-composed) inputs and result in food and non-food agricultural products and/or services, income and access to food, as well as environmental impacts. A food system operates in and is influenced by social, political, cultural, technological, economic and natural environments (HLPE, 2014; UNEP, 2016; Global Panel 2016; HLPE, 2017). Food systems change under the influence of 'driving forces' that emerge from these environments: factors that actors in the system (farmers, traders, suppliers, processors and consumers) cannot directly influence, but which do exert a long-term and therefore lasting influence on the form and the functioning of the food system (Béné et al., 2019a; Fanzo and Davis, 2021).

Food system literature has shown different ways of conceptualising the food system: some include more detail in food system activities, considering more complex interdependences and relationships between activities and outcomes than others (e.g. ShiftN, 2009 versus Van Berkum et al., 2018), some have a greater orientation on (impacts of food system activities and outcomes on) natural resources (e.g. UNEP, 2016), and others on (consequences of food system activities and outcomes for) diets (e.g. GLOPAN, 2016; Zurek et al., 2020).

Moreover, there are multiple narratives of what causes food systems failure and how to improve it (Béné et al., 2018; Dengerink and Brouwer, 2020). These narratives suggest a consideration of the main bottleneck(s) that need(s) to be resolved as a matter of priority, and, in which interventions and investments should be made. For example, a first perspective considers that the inability to feed the future world is the biggest challenge and increasing production (including by means of closing the yield gap) is the solution to that failure. Others point to a shortage of nutritional food and shift the perspective from quantity to quality and to closing the 'diet quality/nutrient gap', with a focus on (micro)nutrient intake and nutritional status of the world population. A third narrative insists on the distributional dimension of the equation, and points to the apparent paradox that although, on aggregate, present food systems are producing enough food to feed the current world population, almost one billion people are still suffering from hunger. In addition to access to food, this approach argues that the economic and social inequalities and inequities that the food systems are generating need to be addressed. And then there is a fourth perspective where the main issue is not so much the yield gap, the nutrient gap or inequity/inequality of the food systems, but rather the negative impact that those modern food systems have on the environment and natural resources, and that the 'footprint' of agricultural activities needs to be reduced.

At the same time, by zooming in on a perceived dominant reason for food system failure, there is a risk that the underlying analytical framework pays (too) little attention to potential trade-offs between interventions and feedback loops in the system. We therefore intend not to let one of the narratives dominate in advance, but instead to follow a 'neutral' perspective in which there is room for addressing different system failures.

A schematic representation of food system activities and their relationships with drivers and outcomes of the food system is shown in Figure 2.1. In this illustration, the core elements of the activities in the supply chain are recognizable, including the food consumers. The drivers and outcomes of the food system included in this illustration are based on the most commonly used conceptualizations of the food system, including HLPE (2017), Béné et al (2019a) and Zurek et al. (2020). The figure is clarified in the rest of the section.

Figure 2.1 Relationships of the food system activities and outcomes to its drivers.

Source: Van Berkum et al., 2018, with adjustments

Figure 2.1 shows that a food system is made up of a number of activities whose primary aim is to ensure food and nutrition security. To emphasize that primary goal, this outcome is explicitly distinguished in the diagram in a separate outcome box (on the right in figure 2.1). Activities in the food system encompass not only activities within the food supply chain, but also service organisations (business services) and the ‘enabling environment’ (e.g. transport, research infrastructure or regulations). A number of factors that influence behaviour at the consumer level are also included: the food environment (i.e. physical and social surroundings that influence what people eat)³ and the characteristics of (individual) consumers, both of which determine the consumer’s relationship to food.

These food system activities contribute to outcomes at the economic level (such as income and employment), social aspects (e.g. added value distribution and workers’ rights), in the areas of the environment (e.g. greenhouse gas emissions and water quality) and food and nutrition security – defined as the use of, access to and availability of food.⁴ These four outcomes interact with one another, and relationships are complex. For example, certain socioeconomic outcomes such as higher income can increase food demand by improved accessibility, yet more food demand may also stimulate increased production which may result in more environmental pressures (by achieving higher production through more chemical input use or by converting natural areas or forest to agricultural us). Better food utilisation by, for instance, reducing food waste could have a positive environmental impact because it can lead to less intensive land use. Trends in the cost of food affect people from different income brackets differently, determining their access to sufficient and healthy food. These examples show there are potentially trade-offs

³ More formally, food environments are defined as the collective physical, economic, policy and socio-cultural surroundings, opportunities and conditions that influence people’s food and beverage choices and consumption (Swinburn et al., 2014; Herforth and Ahmed, 2015).

⁴ Stability is often considered as a cross-cutting factor that is necessary for the others to hold (e.g Upton et al., 2016). Stability also emphasises the importance of continuity and thus draws the time dimension into the system. Stability is not included in this figure because of its overarching nature.

between environmental, socio-economic and food security outcomes, but there may also be synergies indicating that an improvement in one dimension is not at the expense of the other(s).

2.2. Food system drivers further explained

Food systems outcomes are affected by many different factors that intersect and evolve in complex ways. These influential factors are considered “drivers” when their impacts occur consistently over a period of time and thus gradually and durably alter food system activities and outcomes over time (Béné et al., 2019a). Drivers of change are factors that are regarded as exogenous to the process of changes of the food system. Examples are population growth, urbanisation and macroeconomic growth as key socio-economic drivers of change in food demand (in composition and quality) affecting activities (e.g. food production) in and outcomes of the food system. Ecological or environmental drivers are natural resources or factors affected by human intervention which directly or indirectly may bring about a change in the natural resource base that can be used for food production. Climate change, soil nutrients and land use are among the major environmental drivers shaping food systems (e.g. Béné et al., 2019a; Brouwer et al., 2020; Fanzo and Davies, 2021).

In the above figure 2.1 we distinguish six environmental and five socio-economic drivers that we further explain below. The environmental drivers indicate the biophysical context in which the food system operates. These consist of five interacting components:

1. The availability of land for agriculture and livestock farming, and related to this, the quality of soils. Unsustainable agricultural methods can put pressure on soil quality.
2. Climate is defined by the long-term pattern of temperature and precipitation averages and extremes at a location. Climate descriptions can refer to areas that are local, regional or global in scale. Warm and humid conditions such as in a tropical climate provide very different potentials for agricultural production than, for example, a continental climate with distinct seasons. Climate change and variability in weather conditions influence the productivity and resilience of ecosystems and landscapes that produce food.
3. The use of fossil fuels (energy) in agricultural machinery and equipment, refrigeration, storage, processing and transport of food. Fuels used for the production of fertilisers and pesticides are also included in this category. A side effect of burning these fuels is the emission of additional greenhouse gases such as carbon dioxide (CO₂), which contributes to climate change.
4. The use of minerals/microminerals, such as NPK and lime, to enrich soils and various metals such as steel, tin and bauxite for the manufacture of packaging, infrastructure and cookware. The growing scarcity of some minerals poses a challenge for the agricultural system.
5. Biodiversity (the variety of plant and animal life) provides different services to the food system activities, such as biomass and firewood, as well as animals for domestication, microbes that guarantee soil quality and a diversity of plant and animal species that enable pollination. The expansion of the agricultural area into natural habitats and climate change pose a direct threat to biodiversity.
6. Water, as an important source of life. This involves not only the availability of water for irrigation, but also high-quality drinking water for cooking, and water for washing.

The interaction between environmental drivers and food system activities occurs mainly at the level of agricultural production (arable farming, horticulture, livestock farming, fishing), and to a lesser extent at the level of other activities in the value chain, such as processing, distribution, domestic and international trade and consumption. However, activities throughout the value chain can influence the use of natural resources in the primary part of the chain, and solutions aimed at the more efficient use of resources can arise from changes in all parts of the chain.

There are also strong interrelationships between the environmental drivers: the quality of soils depends on the quantity of water and minerals; climate change has put pressure on water availability in many regions; and biodiversity is declining worldwide. However, pressures on water availability or biodiversity impacts of climate change will be different among regions, depending on the starting point regarding natural conditions and the impact of social interactions or behaviour on natural resources. Indeed, the biophysical base of food systems can differ regionally, as soil quality, water availability, temperatures and other basic ecological components that are used in the food system are not the same everywhere in the world.

The socio-economic drivers of the food system can be divided into five categories. This division into these five categories is somewhat arbitrary but it does show concisely and adequately the different aspects that can make up a 'driver' of food systems:

1. **Markets:** changes in market systems, regimes and structures, affecting trade relations and how factor (land, labour and capital) and food price are determined in the food system. Markets provide opportunities for matching food supply and demand, but but market concentration (i.e., a few firms dominating market supply or demand) can also strongly influence market prices. Food markets are highly affected by the process of globalization, which increases the interconnectedness of populations around the world. Globalisation and trade have contributed to the integration of global markets, direct investment by foreign companies, the expansion of transnational food companies and cross-cultural marketing of food products. These factors affect the type, quantity, quality, cost and desirability of foods available to consumers (Fanzo and Davies, 2021). Note also that in some conceptualizations of food systems (e.g. Zurek et al., 2020; Acs et al., 2025), population and macroeconomic growth are also explicitly included as driving factors. However, we view these factors as factors that help determine structural changes in food markets, i.e. as underlying forces of market changes. We therefore do not explicitly include population and macroeconomic growth in our visualization of the food system.
2. **Policy & governance:** different kinds of policy – for example, on land rights, food security, the environment, labour, trade or food safety – can influence the food system. Policy seeks to guide the outcomes of food system activities in a socially desired direction, but outcomes are sometimes different to what is expected or policy measures do not align with the private interests of actors in the food system. Governance relates to decision-making, implementation, accountability and other processes and mechanisms that lead to food system outcomes. This concerns the extent to which all stakeholders (private companies, consumers, environmental organizations, research organizations, etc.) can influence food and nutrition governance. Power dynamics play an important role in decision-making (Fanzo and Davies 2021).
3. **Science & Technology:** research, innovation and education in key areas for agriculture and nutrition, such as chain agreements, transport/logistics and medical or food technology. Research and innovation are important drivers for the productivity growth of all food system activities and can improve the quality and nutritional value of production.

Technical or organisational innovations can also contribute to a more sustainable food system.

4. **Social organisations:** organisational forms or sectors that affect the functioning of the food system, such as households, social movements, media, education and health care. For example, farmers' cooperatives can help strengthen the bargaining position of farmers in the food system and possibly result in higher incomes. On the consumer side, for example, nutrition societies inform and promote healthy food choices to contribute to a more informed and healthier food intake of consumers.
5. **Individual factors:** the lifestyle, norms (e.g. animal welfare norms), attitudes and cultures (e.g. halal) that influence the choices of individual actors in the food system. These factors can be place-related and can influence consumer choices. Conversely, the food system can exert influence on individual factors, for example through home delivery of ready-made meals and/or groceries (appealing to a modern lifestyle).

Each of these socio-economic drivers has the potential to influence food system activities but can in turn also be affected by the activities and actors in the system. This can give rise to multiplier effects or feedback mechanisms.

2.3. On boundary setting of the food system

Defining drivers of the food system - that is, the external factors that have a lasting and long-term influence on the behaviour of actors in the food system but that are not directly influenced by those actors - also raises the question of what the boundaries of a food system are. Systems thinkers including Churchman (1968) and Ulrich (1983; 2002) make clear that, when defining the boundaries of a food system, it is crucial to recognize that any analysis will inevitably be partial and incomplete. The complexity of food systems makes it impossible to capture every aspect objectively, leading to subjective choices about what to include and exclude. These choices influence not only the results of the analysis but also the subsequent policy recommendations.

Furthermore, the normative nature of boundary setting, rooted in value judgments, shapes our understanding of what constitutes a desirable outcome and what areas require improvement. As Helfgott and Midgley (2020) emphasize, this inherent partiality can result in incomplete conclusions and recommendations, potentially overlooking critical interactions and problems within the system. For instance, a study focusing solely on increasing agricultural production might overlook the environmental impact of intensive farming practices or the social consequences of neglecting small-scale farmers.

Therefore, transparency in boundary setting is essential (Van Berkum, 2021). Researchers should explicitly state the scope of their analysis, the rationale behind their choices, and the potential limitations of their findings. This transparency allows for a more informed interpretation of the results and facilitates a broader discussion about the trade-offs involved in different policy options. Ultimately, acknowledging the limitations of boundary setting enables a more nuanced and comprehensive understanding of food systems, leading to more effective and sustainable solutions.

For our purposes, it is good to be clear about where we draw the boundaries of the EU food system. This may not be as easy as it seems on first sight. First of all, the focus is the geographical designation of the EU, the 27 Member States and their regions. Most food produced in the EU is consumed within the EU. However, the EU food system is strongly connected to countries outside the EU, through imports and exports. This includes production outside of the EU for EU

consumers, next to commodities, energy and fertilisers for EU processors and farmers but also production in the EU for non-EU users (both in the food supply chain and end-consumers). Non-EU countries and global regions are distinguished as they are relevant to our analyses. Ukraine has a special place, because of the political decision that this country could eventually become an EU member state: Ukraine has been a candidate member of the European Union since June 2022 and accession talks started in June 2024. Future membership of such a large, largely agricultural country as Ukraine will most likely have far-reaching consequences for the agricultural policy in an enlarged EU.

In this project, the more explicit desire is to be able to analyse the effects of policy interventions for all actors in the food system, so besides farmers/fishermen also for traders, processors, retailers and consumers of food. In addition, for a grounded insight into policy impact on the outcomes of the food system, the analyses will have to address the economic, social and environmental dimensions. Thus, ACT4CAP27 stands for a holistic approach with regard to food system activities as well as to food system outcomes.

2.4. Usability of the food systems approach in informing policies aimed at transformative action

A defining feature of systems thinking is that it views the behaviour of a system as an interplay of interacting subsystems, in which feedback plays a key role, rather than as a simple chain of cause-effect relationships (Ericksen, 2008). This also distinguishes systems thinking from other approaches such as farming systems, sector or chain approaches, in which interventions are often designed to make optimum use of the means of production (natural resources, labour, capital). This usually involves applying technological innovations at the level of family businesses, sectors and/or chains, with the focus on raising productivity and profitability. Although those approaches also analyse the impact of interventions on the market (prices, incomes) and environment (CO₂ emissions), and the depletion of natural resources (such as erosion or water shortage), they tend to pay insufficient attention to feedback from the socio-economic system and/or ecosystem to the farm, sector or the supply chain. Food systems thinking steps back as it were from the place where the intervention occurs, thereby providing an opportunity when analysing the outcomes of policy interventions to include feedback from outcomes outside the activities that relate directly to food production and consumption. This also makes a food system approach (FSA) a useful perspective in the literature on the resilience (robustness) of the food production system, which is about the capacity of the system to absorb shocks, such as an animal disease crisis or trade boycott. Climate change is an example of a ‘shock’ with a long-term dimension.

The sustainable use of natural resources in relation to the growing need for food is a key focus in the literature on resilience (e.g. Ge et al., 2017; Sgarbi and Nadeu, 2023) and ways are being sought to make food production less vulnerable to these shocks. The solution approaches emphasised in this literature include the need for climate-smart agriculture (a combination of increasing agricultural productivity and reducing greenhouse gas emissions), supplemented by policy aimed at trade, supplies and nutrition and social policy options. This is because the availability of food does not guarantee that people can also access it. Integrated system solutions are advocated, in which an FSA – because of its holistic nature – is a more appropriate analytical framework than an approach that focuses solely on the production component (Ge et al., 2017; Zurek et al., 2020).

Thus, unlike a focus on a value chain or farming system, the FSA looks at the interactions within the food system and its socio-economic and biophysical environment. It also highlights policy pathways that do not intervene in the value chain itself, but in the context of the food production system. These include, for instance, a tax on ‘unhealthy’ nutrition or promoting investments in the infrastructure needed for the production, storage and transport of – usually perishable – vegetables and fruit (regarded as the most nutritious foods). And by providing a broader view of the impact of different intervention strategies, it helps in the weighing-up of particular policy choices. The FSA thus provides insights into opportunities for effective entry points for longer-term policy and offers at least three benefits (Van Berkum et al. 2018). First, it provides a checklist of topics that should at the very least be addressed when it comes to improving food and nutrition security, certainly in relation to other policy objectives such as reducing environmental pressures or social inequality. Second, FSA helps to map the impact of environmental and climate changes on food and nutrition security by pointing to the various vulnerabilities of the food system. In that sense the approach can contribute to the search for possibilities for strengthening the system’s resilience to climate changes. Third, it helps to determine the most limiting factors for achieving food and nutrition security, and hence identify effective interventions aimed at improving food and nutrition security.

To illustrate already here how the conceptual framework can be useful in evaluating the CAP (a key driver of behavior by actors in the food system), we highlight the direct and indirect effects of the policy, which reveal the interrelationships between actors in the food system and show supply chain dynamics. CAP policies directly influence producers through income support, coupled payments, and environmental cross-compliance. These payments affect production choices, input usage, and structural changes on farms (e.g. Lillemets et al., 2022). Policies create ripple effects, influencing upstream suppliers (e.g., machinery, seeds) and downstream actors (e.g., processors, retailers). For instance, high internal EU prices for commodities like cereals and dairy—stimulated by past CAP regimes—impact the competitiveness of downstream food processors and influence import/export patterns. Moreover, policies aimed at sustainability, such as reducing pesticides and improving animal welfare, compel processors and retailers to adapt their procurement and supply chain management practices.

Policy levers to enhance food system competitiveness and sustainability can be implemented on different levels and actors in the food system. For instance, the current CAP strengthens the role of POs/IBOs (Producer Organisations and Interbranch Organisations), allowing them to cooperate across sectors to improve market power, manage risks, and enhance efficiency (see for examples the EU-CAP Network policy brief 2024). Direct Payments and Eco-schemes are tools used to incentivize greener production methods, forcing adoption of new technologies and practices across the supply chain. The interaction between CAP and international trade agreements influences the competitiveness of EU exporters and impacts the import of commodities, which directly affects the stability of supply.

Each of these measures often focuses on a single actor in the supply chain, but they have an impact throughout the entire chain. For example, to successfully implement incentives for farmers to cultivate more sustainably, retailers will need to change their purchasing requirements, and pesticide manufacturers will need to offer more environmentally friendly (but still effective) products. Trade agreements that lead to increased imports (benefiting both consumers and the industries that import raw materials) and competition for farmers could encourage farmers to adopt more intensive production methods with potentially negative environmental consequences. Mutual dependencies are reinforced by the intensive relationships between the

supply chain partners, and policy objectives can have undesirable side effects. This necessitates a more holistic approach to considering the consequences of agricultural and food-related policies—by analyzing them through a food systems lens.

2.5 In conclusion

European policies increasingly aim for sustainability and include food security and economic objectives alongside environmental and social objectives. However, there may be important trade-offs: interventions that support objectives in one area may jeopardise objectives in others.

The concept of food systems and the mapping of components and interrelationships between actor behaviour, drivers and outcomes of food systems help to map the broader scope of potential impacts of interventions on potentially competing policy objectives. Tools to address such potential trade-offs (but also to identify potential synergies) are needed to provide stakeholders with evidence-based information on the effects of policy and investment interventions. In the application of food system analyses, clarity is important around what belongs to the system and what does not: which activities in the food system are central, which policies and for what purpose? To achieve this, the next section discusses what is meant by aiming for sustainable food systems.

3. FOOD SYSTEMS AND SOCIETAL GOALS: HOW TO UNDERSTAND SUSTAINABLE FOOD SYSTEMS

3.1. Introduction

In the previous chapter, the components and the mutual relationships between these components of a food system were indicated and explained. In this chapter, we discuss in more detail the societal goals of a food system. There is broad recognition by governments and policy makers that food systems must be sustainable and produce sufficient healthy food within planetary boundaries (e.g. UN Food system summit 2021). In this chapter, we briefly review how the scope of the key concepts of food security and sustainability as societally desirable outcomes of the food system has evolved over time and what that implies for monitoring food system outcomes.

3.2. Evolving definition of sustainable food and nutrition security

A well-functioning food system must supply sufficient and healthy food at affordable prices without exceeding planetary ecological boundaries (UN Food System Summit 2021; IFAD, 2021; FAO, 2018; EC, 2020). Over the years, different terms and terminologies have been used to describe the (desired) outcomes of a working food system. These terms come from different scientific communities, such as the agricultural, development or nutrition communities, and reflect the main discourses of the time (Zurek et al., 2020; Clapp et al., 2022). First definitions of food security formulated in the 1940s were further elaborated in the 1970s, 1980s and 1990s by placing more emphasis on the nutrition and access dimensions. This led to the officially accepted definition of Food and Nutrition Security that was proposed in 1996 and modified in 2002 (FAO 2002). It is included in the 2009 Declaration of the World Summit on Food Security and states: *“Food security [is] a situation that exists when all people, at all times, have physical, social and economic access to sufficient, safe and nutritious food that meets their dietary needs and food preferences for an active and healthy life”*. Although still an important dimension of food security, availability is not explicitly mentioned anymore in this definition, in which ‘at all times’, ‘access’ and ‘sufficient, safe and nutritious’ are the key words. When originally coined about 20 years ago, the word ‘sufficient’ referred to those with insufficient food. Nowadays it equally applies to those with too much.

The concept has since been expanded and now also includes sustainability aspects in a broad sense. Initially by agreeing on a definition of healthy and sustainable diets as *“those diets with a low impact on the environment that contribute to food and nutrition security and healthy living for current and future generations. Sustainable diets are protective and respectful of biodiversity and ecosystems, culturally acceptable, accessible, economically fair and affordable; nutritionally adequate, safe and healthy; while optimizing natural and human resources.”* (FAO, 2010). A recent joint statement by FAO and WHO (2024) refers to healthy diet as one that meets four core principles, including *“adequacy (providing enough essential nutrients to prevent deficiencies and promote health, without excess); balanced (in energy intake, and energy sources to promote healthy weight, growth, and disease prevention); moderate (in consumption of foods, nutrients or other compounds associated with detrimental health effects), and diverse (including a wide variety of nutritious foods within and across food groups to favour nutrient adequacy and consumption of other health promoting substances)”* (FAO and WHO, 2024:2).

Balanced diets are also an integrated part of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which emphasize that a balanced diet should also include other dimensions such as environmental and economic sustainability and ethical aspects, among others (Assembly & Goals 2015)⁵. Furthermore, sustainable, balanced diets should also include the needs for both the economically disadvantaged and future generations. A sustainable food system therefore also has a clear social dimension, where a food system to be considered sustainable from a social perspective ensures food security to the present and future generations, gender and race equity, as well as fair work conditions. FAO (2018) defines a sustainable food system as: *“a food system that delivers food security and nutrition for all in such a way that the economic, social and environmental bases to generate food security and nutrition for future generations are not compromised”*.

In the international policy dialogue on global food security, there is increasing recognition of the influence of power relations on food and nutrition security, specifically the adverse effects of concentrations of corporate power on the disposition options of small-scale farmers and other entrepreneurs and vulnerable groups in society. In the High Level Panel of Experts on Food Security and Nutrition of the Committee on World Food Security (HLPE-FSN), the action perspective for countering power inequality is referred to as ‘agency’ (HLPE, 2023). In addition, there is broad recognition that sustainability (particularly in the sense of ecological sustainability) is indispensable in the long term as a prerequisite for future food security. This offers complementarity to the dimension of stability, which is explained as the pursuit of robust outcomes on the four dimensions (i.e. availability, access, utilization and stability) of food and nutrition security in the event of short-term shocks. The HLPE-FSN recommends adding agency and sustainability to the four widely accepted dimensions of food and nutrition security (see Clapp et al., 2022).

Recognition of the importance of agency and sustainability in policy contexts would thus pave the way for more nuanced analysis as well as more concrete policy pathways to address systemic inequities within food systems.

The expanding dimensions of food and nutrition security, with the inclusion of sustainability and agency, have significant implications for the metrics used to measure and monitor progress (Helfgott and Midgley 2020). While traditional metrics focused on food availability, access, utilization, and stability remain important, they are no longer sufficient to capture the full complexity of food security in the 21st century (Béné et al. 2019a; Ericksen, 2008) and new metrics are needed to assess:

- **Sustainability:** This requires measuring the environmental impacts of food production, consumption, and waste, including greenhouse gas emissions, water quality, soil fertility and biodiversity loss (UNEP, 2016). It also necessitates assessing the social and economic sustainability of food systems, such as fair labour practices, equitable distribution of resources, and resilience to shocks (Van Berkum et al. 2018).
- **Agency:** Measuring agency involves assessing people's empowerment and ability to make their own choices about food (HLPE, 2017). This includes factors such as access to information, participation in decision-making processes, and control over resources (Jagustovića et al. 2019). Clapp et al (2022), for instance, suggests that measures of agency dimensions could include conditions that empower consumers over food

⁵ For instance, SDG 2 explicitly ties sustainability to food security in its call to: “End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture.”

purchase and consumption, such as more precise labelling and nutritional information as well as information on social, economic and environmental conditions under which the food was produced.

Furthermore, the interlinkages between these dimensions need to be considered (GLOPAN 2016). For example, agency can contribute to both nutritional outcomes and environmental sustainability by empowering people to adopt more sustainable and healthy diets.

Therefore, a comprehensive monitoring framework should include a mix of quantitative and qualitative indicators that capture the multi-dimensional nature of food and nutrition security and, take into account the behaviour of all actors in the food chain (in addition to farmers, processors, traders, also consumers). This will enable a more nuanced understanding of the challenges and progress towards achieving sustainable and equitable food systems for all.

3.3. Sustainability in food systems

As is clear from the above, sustainability is not limited to the ecological sustainability of food production but rather emphasises the connections between ecosystems, food, society and political economy to sustain food systems and support food security now and in the future (HLPE, 2020). Hence, in developing a sustainable food system, sustainability should be assessed holistically. To be sustainable, food system development should generate positive value along three dimensions simultaneously: economic, social and environmental. Figure 3.1 below is an illustration of how sustainability in food systems is defined (adapted from FAO 2018).⁶

Economically, a food system is considered sustainable if the activities carried out by each food system actor or supporting service provider are economically viable. The activities must generate benefits or economic added value for all categories of stakeholders: wages for workers, taxes for governments, profits for companies and improvements in the food supply for consumers. Socially, a food system is considered sustainable if there is equity in the distribution of economic added value, taking into account vulnerable groups such as women or young people. Fundamentally, food system activities must contribute to the promotion of important socio-cultural outcomes, such as nutrition and health, working conditions and animal welfare. Institutions are important social constructs of managing processes and practices through which issues of common concern are decided upon and regulated. In the environmental domain, sustainability is determined by ensuring that the impact of food system activities on the surrounding natural environment is neutral or positive, taking into account biodiversity, water, soil, animal and plant health, carbon and water footprints, food loss and waste, and toxicity.

⁶ Note that in this illustration, food and nutrition (& health) security is considered under Social impacts, whereas in Figure 2.1 Food and nutrition security is defined as a separate food system outcome dimension, which is to highlight that a food system is made up of activities which prime aim is to increase food and nutrition security.

Figure 3.1 Sustainable food systems.

Source: FAO, 2018

Figure 3.1 provides a comprehensive overview of the three dimensions of impacts associated with sustainable food systems: economic, social, and environmental. These dimensions are interconnected. This means that working towards a sustainable food system means that every measure taken or investment made to achieve the transition to a sustainable food system must contribute to one or more dimensions but without compromising the other(s). It follows that identifying trade-offs and synergies between policy objectives and measures is a key activity in conducting analyses of policy impacts on food system outcomes. Interventions may have a positive socio-economic outcome (e.g. improving income generation) for some of the stakeholders involved, or a positive socio-economic effect may go hand-in-hand with negative environmental consequences (e.g. water pollution). Trade-offs among stakeholders and between sustainability objectives need to be considered and to be taken into account. In case trade-offs occur, alternative or additional measures may be considered. The key principle is that interventions are designed to improve at least one of the sustainability dimensions without compromising another.

4. FOOD SYSTEM OUTCOMES AND EU'S GREEN DEAL AND CAP POLICIES

4.1. Mapping food system outcomes to EU policy objectives

The food system, encompassing all activities related to food production (i.e. farming), processing, distribution, consumption, and waste management, is crucial for human well-being and societal development. However, it faces numerous challenges, including ensuring food security for a growing population, promoting social equity and fair working conditions, maintaining economic viability for farmers and other actors in the food chain, and mitigating the environmental impacts of food production (HLPE, 2017). Public policies must help address these challenges and support public and private actors achieving the aforementioned societal goals. How does EU policy contribute to the desired outcomes of the food system? In this chapter, we connect our concept of the food system with the objectives of (intended) EU policy. Mapping the food system framework with EU policies shows EU's main areas of concern regarding a sustainable food system. This mapping of the food system concept with EU's public policies also indicates where measurements of policy impacts on food system outcomes should be focused on, and what our modelling tools should be ready for. Table 4.1 provides a mapping of key food system dimensions to the objectives outlined in the CAP strategic plan and the EGD. This mapping highlights how these policies aim to address the multifaceted challenges facing the food system, with a focus on ensuring food security, social equity, economic viability, and environmental sustainability.

The CAP, a central pillar of the EU's agricultural policy, plays a critical role in shaping the food system. Its objectives, as outlined in the CAP Strategic Plans Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2021/2115), include supporting farm incomes, ensuring sustainable agriculture and food production, enhancing market orientation and competitiveness, and contributing to climate action and environmental protection. The EGD, a comprehensive policy framework aimed at achieving climate neutrality and environmental sustainability, includes several strategies that directly address food system challenges (EC, 2019). These include the F2F Strategy (EC, 2020a), which promotes sustainable food production and consumption, the Biodiversity Strategy (EC, 2020b), which aims to protect and restore biodiversity, and the Soil Strategy (EC, 2021), which focuses on soil health and sustainable soil management.

Table 4.1. demonstrates how the CAP objectives and the EGD strategies intersect and complement each other in addressing the various dimensions of the food system. For example, the CAP objective of ensuring sustainable agriculture and food production aligns with the F2F Strategy's goal of promoting sustainable food production and reducing food loss and waste. Similarly, the CAP objective of improving farmers' position in the value chain complements the F2F Strategy's aim to ensure fair incomes for farmers and promote fair trading practices.

By mapping the food system dimensions to the CAP and EGD objectives, the table provides a comprehensive overview of how these policies intend to contribute to a more sustainable, equitable, and resilient food system.

Table 4.1. Mapping Food system dimensions to EGD and CAP objectives

Food systems dimensions, areas and indicator domains			CAP	EGD Strategies			
Dimension	Thematic area	Indicator domain	Objective	F2F	Biodiversity	Soil	Climate
Food security	Nutrition security	Food availability Food affordability	Support viable farm income and resilience across the Union to enhance food security	Promotes sustainable food production, reduced food loss and waste, and healthy diets.	Supports healthy ecosystems for food production.	Healthy soils are essential for food production.	Climate action is crucial for safeguarding food security.
		Diet quality/food utilization/diet diversity; Food waste	Improve the response of EU agriculture to societal demand on food and health, including safe, nutritious and sustainable food, reducing food waste				
Social	Health	Live expectancy; obesity; animal welfare	Modernize agriculture and strengthen its resilience: includes supporting young farmers and promoting gender equality in agriculture	Promotes healthy diets and safe food			
	Equity	Gender equality; position of youth	Improve farmers' position in the value chain	Promotes fair economic returns for farmers and decent working conditions.	Can have social implications related to access to natural resources.		
		Income distribution (along the supply chain)					
Economic	Income	Farmers' income	Improve farmers' position in the value chain	Aims to strengthen the economic sustainability of the food system, including fair prices for farmers.			
	Value added in supply chain	Value added	improve farmers' position in the value chain	Promotes efficient and sustainable food systems, which can impact sectoral employment and value added			

Food systems dimensions, areas and indicator domains			CAP	EGD Strategies			
Dimension	Thematic area	Indicator domain	Objective	F2F	Biodiversity	Soil	Climate
Environment	Biodiversity	Genetic diversity, Species diversity, Ecosystem diversity	Contribute to the protection of biodiversity, enhance ecosystem services and preserve habitats and landscapes	Promotes practices to reduce environmental impacts, including protecting biodiversity.	Directly addresses biodiversity conservation and restoration.		
	Land use	Agricultural land use	<i>Contribute to climate action and the environment:</i> This objective includes promoting sustainable land management practices to protect soil and water resources. Foster sustainable development and efficient management of natural resources such as water, soil and air	Promotes sustainable land management practices.	Addresses land-use impacts on biodiversity.		
	Water use	Agricultural water use		Promotes water efficiency in agriculture.			
	Nutrient flows	Nitrogen, Phosphate, Potassium in use in agriculture	<i>Contribute to climate action and the environment:</i> This objective includes reducing nutrient pollution from agriculture.	Addresses nutrient pollution from agriculture.		Focuses on nutrient management for soil health.	
	Chemical pollution	Use of pesticides, use of fertilizers	<i>Contribute to climate action and the environment:</i> This objective includes reducing the use of pesticides and fertilizers.	Aims to reduce chemical pollution from pesticides and fertilizers.			
	Climate	GHG emissions, ammonia emissions	Contribute to climate change mitigation and adaptation, as well as sustainable energy	Promotes climate-smart agriculture and reduced greenhouse gas emissions.			Addresses climate change mitigation and adaptation in the food system.

Note to this table: Food systems dimensions are the four dimensions defined in our Conceptual Framework in Fig 2.1. Thematic areas are taken from BrightSpace D1.1. Policy objectives are linked to these Thematic areas, based on underlying EU communication documents – see reference list. We have added indicator domains that we see as necessary to include in order to address the broader food system outcomes in particular in the Social and Economic

dimension so that we better capture impacts of GD/F2F and CAP policies on consumers/health and on the actors in the food supply chain other than farmers

In the following subsections the link between EGD and the four key food system outcomes were analysed in more details. This involves examining how EGD policies and strategies directly and indirectly influence each of these outcomes. Also potential challenges and limitations in achieving the EGD's goals and explored future policy options for a more safe and just EU food system are discussed.

4.2 Environmental outcomes of food systems and the EGD

Direct and Indirect Impact

The EGD is a driving force for positive change in the environmental dimension of our food systems (EC, 2019). The F2F Strategy's goal to slash pesticide use by 50% by 2030 is a significant step towards protecting biodiversity and reducing water pollution (EC, 2020a). By actively supporting organic farming, the EGD aims to promote practices that improve soil health and enhance biodiversity. However, it's important to note that while organic farming can contribute to improved soil health, this outcome is not guaranteed and depends heavily on the specific management practices employed by the farmer, just as poor management can deplete soils in conventional farming. Regarding greenhouse gas emissions, the relationship with organic farming is complex (e.g. WRI, 2019; Smith et al., 2019; Bocean, 2025). While some organic practices can reduce emissions, concerns have been raised about potentially higher overall emissions per unit of output due to lower yields and potential leakage effects, which warrants careful consideration and further research. Furthermore, the emphasis on reducing food waste minimizes the environmental footprint of food production and consumption, including land and water use, and greenhouse gas emissions.

Beyond these direct impacts, the EGD's strategies also have indirect environmental benefits. The Biodiversity Strategy is crucial for protecting and restoring biodiversity, which underpins vital ecosystem services like pollination and pest control (European Commission, 2020b). The EGD's commitment to climate action helps mitigate climate change, safeguarding ecosystems and biodiversity from its harmful effects (EC, 2019). Finally, the Soil Strategy, by focusing on improving soil health, contributes to enhanced soil fertility, reduced erosion, and improved water retention, all of which are vital for a healthy environment and sustainable food production (EC, 2021).

Manageable trade-offs, hard constraints and policy options

Balancing environmental sustainability with food security and economic growth can be complex, requiring careful consideration of trade-offs and potential unintended consequences. Effective implementation of the EGD's strategies also hinges on significant investments and policy changes at both EU and national levels, demanding coordinated effort and political will. Furthermore, while global factors such as climate change can significantly impact food systems, it's important to note that the EU is actively taking steps to influence international trade in a more sustainable direction. Initiatives like the EGD's focus on sustainable imports and specific regulations such as the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) demonstrate the EU's efforts to extend its environmental standards and promote sustainability beyond its borders. Other examples of the EU's influence in this area also exist such as the EU Deforestation Regulation and are evolving.

4.3 Food Security and the EGD

Direct and Indirect Impacts

The EGD, and in particular its F2F Strategy, can potentially influence food security through a variety of mechanisms. Firstly, by aiming to halve food waste by 2030, the F2F Strategy directly increases the amount of food available for consumption (EC, 2020a). This aligns with the broader goal of reducing food loss and waste, a critical aspect of enhancing food security (FAO, 2019). Secondly, the EGD promotes sustainable agricultural practices that enhance productivity and bolster resilience against the challenges of climate change. This is crucial for maintaining food production in the face of environmental pressures, as climate change is a significant threat to agricultural yields (IPCC, 2019). Furthermore, the emphasis on fair trade and equitable working conditions within the F2F Strategy (and repeated in DG AGRI's Vision document of 2025) fosters a more stable and just food system, contributing to long-term food security by ensuring that producers receive fair returns and are incentivized to maintain production.

Beyond these direct impacts, the EGD also influences food security indirectly. Its commitment to climate action, including reducing greenhouse gas emissions from agriculture, helps to mitigate the detrimental effects of climate change on food production (EC, 2019). Similarly, the EGD's Biodiversity Strategy, with its focus on protecting and restoring ecosystems, safeguards crucial services such as pollination, pest control, and soil fertility, all of which underpin food production (EC, 2020b). Finally, by prioritizing soil health, the EGD promotes the long-term productivity and resilience of agricultural land, further contributing to food security (EC, 2021).

Manageable trade-offs and hard constraints

While the EGD holds great promise for enhancing food security, it is necessary to acknowledge the inherent potential trade-offs and constraints, many of which have been forcefully articulated by stakeholders and are reflected in recent policy adjustments. The relationship between the EGD and food security is fraught with tensions, a reality underscored by widespread farmer protests across the EU and critical assessments from international bodies. A central concern is that the initial framing of the EGD's impact on food security may have presented an overly optimistic picture, downplaying significant trade-offs. Many stakeholders, including farmers and some international observers, perceive a direct conflict between the EGD's environmental objectives and the imperative of maintaining robust food production levels.

For instance, studies such as the USDA Economic Research Service report (Beckman et al., 2023) project that the EGD's targeted reductions in agricultural inputs (e.g., land set-aside for biodiversity, reduced use of fertilizers and pesticides) could lead to a decline in EU agricultural production by 7 to 12 percent under an EU-only adoption scenario.⁹ Such a decline, if realized, could impact the EU's contribution to global food supplies and potentially increase worldwide food prices by 9 to 89 percent, depending on the global adoption scenario (Beckman et al., 2023). This raises serious concerns about food security for vulnerable populations worldwide, with the same USDA ERS report estimating an increase in the number of food-insecure people globally by 22 million (EU-only adoption) to 185 million (global adoption). Indeed, rural populations and farmers themselves often experience food insecurity, and European countries are not immune to the socioeconomic consequences of high food prices (Lovec et al., 2023). If environmental goals lead to production declines and price hikes, the food security goal of affordable and available food is challenged, forming a core reason for farmer protests.

Furthermore, the strategy to reduce food loss and waste, while beneficial for resource efficiency and overall food availability, presents complex economic trade-offs at the producer level. As pointed out by Rutten (2013) and supported by analyses like the JRC report by Britz et al., 2019, a significant reduction in food waste can lead to decreased demand for primary agricultural products. From an economic standpoint, food waste represents a form of demand; reducing this "demand" can lead to a surplus of primary agricultural products if production levels remain constant in the short term. This, in turn, can cause downward pressure on farm-gate prices and incomes, potentially impacting the economic viability of farmers, particularly smallholders or those producing perishable goods (Britz et al., 2019).

The successful implementation of the EGD's ambitious strategies also hinges on substantial investments and policy reforms at both the EU and national levels, requiring coordinated effort and political will (EC, 2019). The socio-economic trade-offs, particularly concerning food production capacity and farm viability, appear to have been initially underestimated or inadequately addressed, forcing a re-evaluation of the pace and intensity of the green transition in agriculture. The recent shift in EU rhetoric towards a new 'Vision for Agriculture and Food' (which has been reported as replacing the Farm to Fork strategy), emphasizing economic sustainability, resilience, simplification, and farmer income, suggests an acknowledgment of these hard constraints and an attempt to rebalance environmental ambitions with the immediate economic and food production concerns of the agricultural sector.¹⁸ Finally, it's crucial to recognize that food security is a global issue, and the EU's policies, while impactful, cannot single-handedly address all the factors influencing food availability and affordability worldwide.

4.3. Social dimension outcomes of food systems and the EGD

Direct and Indirect Impact

The EGD, particularly its F2F Strategy, has a large impact on the social dimension of EU's food systems. The F2F Strategy actively promotes healthy and sustainable diets by encouraging the consumption of fruits, vegetables, and whole grains while discouraging the consumption of unhealthy foods (EC, 2020a). This shift towards healthier eating habits has far-reaching implications for public health and well-being, as diet-related diseases are a major public health concern (WHO, 2020). Furthermore, the F2F Strategy champions fair trade practices and decent working conditions for farmers and agricultural workers, ensuring that those who produce our food are treated with dignity and respect. This aims to address issues of social equity and labour rights within the food supply chain (ILO, 2016). By supporting sustainable agriculture and reducing food waste, the EGD also plays a vital role in reducing food poverty and insecurity, ensuring that everyone has access to nutritious food.

Beyond these direct impacts, the EGD's strategies also indirectly influence the social dimension of food systems. The Biodiversity Strategy, for instance, protects biodiversity and the crucial ecosystem services it provides, such as pollination and pest control, which are essential for food production and human health (EC, 2020b). Similarly, the EGD's climate action goals contribute to mitigating climate change, safeguarding human health from its detrimental effects, such as heat stress and air pollution (EC, 2019). Finally, the Soil Strategy, by focusing on improving soil health, not only enhances food production but also contributes to better nutrition and overall health (EC, 2021).

Manageable trade-offs and hard constraints

While the EGD's target is aimed in improving the social dimension of food systems, several trade-offs and constraints may off-set its full sustainability potential. Achieving the EGD's social objectives, such as promoting healthier diets for all and ensuring fair incomes, encounters significant hurdles related to food affordability and distributional equity. A critical concern is that measures promoting sustainability, such as stricter environmental standards or a shift towards organic farming, could increase on-farm production costs (INRAE, 2024). If these costs are not fully absorbed by farmers (thereby reducing their income) or covered by subsidies, they are likely to be passed on to consumers in the form of higher food prices. Such price increases disproportionately affect low-income households, which spend a larger percentage of their budget on food. This can reduce their access to nutritious food and potentially widen health and social inequalities, as these households may be forced to choose cheaper, less healthy alternatives (European Parliament, Committee on the Environment, Public Health and Food Safety, 2024.) This dynamic creates a complex challenge, as highlighted by analyses in, for instance, Swinnen (2010), which emphasize that policies can have divergent impacts on the food security of poor consumers versus poor producers. If sustainable food options become premium-priced, the goal of widespread adoption of healthy diets may be undermined for vulnerable populations.

Furthermore, the economic effects of initiatives like food waste reduction, while environmentally sound and intended to increase overall food availability, can have unintended social consequences for primary producers. As discussed in previous sections, a sharp decrease in demand for agricultural products due to less waste in the supply chain can lower farm-gate prices and incomes (Britz et al. 2019). This can negatively impact the livelihoods and social well-being of farming communities, especially smaller or more vulnerable agricultural operations. This highlights the challenge of ensuring that achieving of one EGD objective (e.g., waste reduction) does not inadvertently undermine others, such as ensuring fair incomes for all actors in the food supply chain. The potential for such potentially counterproductive outcomes highlights the importance of targeted support mechanisms and inclusive policy design to mitigate adverse distributional effects (Lang & Heasman, 2015).

To further enhance the social dimension of food systems, the EU could prioritize investing in education and awareness campaigns that promote healthy and sustainable diets. These campaigns can empower consumers to make informed food choices that benefit both their health and the environment (EC, 2020a). Additionally, strengthening social safety nets is crucial to ensure that everyone, regardless of their socioeconomic status, has access to affordable and nutritious food. This can help alleviate food insecurity and promote social equity (FAO, 2020). Finally, supporting local food systems can foster social cohesion and stimulate economic development within communities, creating a more resilient and equitable food system overall (Marsden, 2003).

4.4. Economic outcomes of food systems and the EGD

Direct & Indirect Impact

The EGD, and especially its F2F Strategy, has a direct influence on the economic aspects of our food systems. The F2F Strategy is designed to ensure fair incomes for farmers by promoting fair trade practices and addressing power imbalances within the food supply chain (EC, 2020a). This fosters a more equitable and sustainable economic environment for those who produce our food. Furthermore, the EGD's support for sustainable agriculture practices contributes to economic growth in rural areas, creating jobs and invigorating local economies. By encouraging innovation

and entrepreneurship in the food sector, the EGD also stimulates the development of new products, services, and business models, driving economic development and competitiveness.

Protecting biodiversity, another key goal of the EGD, contributes to the long-term economic viability of agriculture and food systems, as biodiversity underpins essential ecosystem services for food production (TEEB, 2010). However, it's important to acknowledge a potential trade-off associated with increasing biodiversity within agricultural landscapes. Allocating land for biodiversity-rich areas might lead to a reduction in the total land available for agricultural production. This necessitates careful consideration and strategic planning to balance biodiversity goals with the need for sufficient food production and maintain farm viability. Finally, by promoting soil health, the EGD fosters increased agricultural productivity (on the longer-term) and reduced input costs, leading to higher farm incomes and a more resilient agricultural sector (EC, 2021).

Manageable trade-offs and hard constraints

While the EGD has the potential to improve the economic dimension of food systems, some hard constraints and potential trade-offs may limit its full realization. As already pointed out in the previous subsections of this chapter, a major concern is that the emphasis on sustainable production methods will reduce yields and production levels, and increase production costs too. As a result, the EU sector risks losing out to foreign suppliers. These consequences of the policy changes are considered unfair if those foreign suppliers do not have to meet the same sustainability requirements. Moreover, food import dependencies may increase due to lower production levels that may result from more sustainable production practices in the EU. Global market volatility, including fluctuations in commodity prices and exchange rates, presents challenges to the food sector, requiring actors to employ risk management strategies such as future markets and contracts. While it's true that markets inherently experience volatility and that the agricultural sector has demonstrated resilience in the face of significant shocks like the COVID-19 pandemic and the war in Ukraine, the extent to which these mechanisms and this resilience can fully mitigate the impacts of ongoing and potentially increasing global market instability remains a key condition for the EGD's long-term success. Additionally, transitioning to sustainable agriculture practices may require significant upfront investments from farmers, potentially hindering their economic viability, especially in the short term. Finally, consumer preferences for sustainable and healthy food products may not always align with the economic incentives of farmers and food businesses, creating a potential conflict between market demands and sustainability goals.

5 INDICATORS OF SUSTAINABLE FOOD SYSTEMS PERFORMANCE

5.1 Introduction

In the previous sections we have indicated how the EGD components and the CAP can contribute to food system outcomes by linking policy objectives to food system outcomes. For example, we find that CAP specific objectives could affect almost all food system outcomes, either directly (because it is one of the policy objectives) or indirectly, as a side effect. EGD objectives set in other parts than the F2F strategy (that can be considered the basis of the operationalisation of the CAP 2023-2027) are mainly focused on food system outcomes that belong to the environmental and climate dimensions. We'll now turn into the question how EU policies can be evaluated on its contribution to sustainable food system outcomes. To this end, we discuss the tools that have recently been developed to measure the transition of the EU food system. We focus in the first place on the EU Food System Monitoring Dashboard, a tool recently developed by the European Commission's JRC to monitor the sustainability of the EU food system from an environmental, economic and social perspective.⁷ The other dashboard we discuss is the Interactive CAP Indicator Dashboard, developed by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development (DG AGRI). This dashboard assesses the CAP performance and its impact on agriculture and rural development in the EU. It allows stakeholders to monitor and analyse the CAP's progress towards its objectives by building upon the CAP indicator framework. Both tools are an example of monitoring the performance of the food and agricultural system respectively that can be an inspiration for our project to use in some way, either in terms of the structure and proposed (sometimes implicit) relationships, or for the data and proxies for indicators. In this sense, the examples are not templates to follow but references to draw from.

5.2 EU Food system monitoring dashboard

The Food System Monitoring Dashboard aims to assess the sustainability of food production, processing, distribution, and consumption across the European Union (Acs et al., 2025). The dashboard builds on several earlier developed proposals for monitoring food systems (Gustafson et al., 2016; Béné et al., 2019a; Fanzo et al., 2021; Hebinck et al., 2021; Schneider et al., 2023), which vary in perspective, purpose, granularity and contextualization within the broader socio-economic or environmental circumstances. The dashboard is a comprehensive and overarching monitoring framework to monitor the sustainability of the EU food system that integrates the positions, policies and available monitoring systems in the EU region. Moreover, the Dashboard is based on a coherent assessment of the procedures used for the design of an indicator system for monitoring the outcomes, or performance, of the European food system across multiple scales, thematic areas and dimensions. The design of the Dashboard is well-rooted in similar studies at global scale and previous studies at European scale, and extends these into a specific monitoring framework for the EU. Therefore, we use this Dashboard as an important reference for what has been developed so far in the field of indicators to measure food system sustainability and the data coverage and availability issues that arise when developing the approach. We are not proposing to copy the Dashboard structure and indicators, but are convinced that this knowledge and information gained in the process of arriving at the Dashboard can give us

⁷ See https://datam.jrc.ec.europa.eu/datam/mashup/EU_FOOD_SYSTEM_MONITORING/index.html

important insights for our search into the most useful and feasible improvements of our four models in the ACT4CAP 27 project in order to be able to perform food system analyses.

The thematic areas and domains of what is termed the EU Food System Sustainability Model in JRC's developed monitoring framework are presented in Table 5.1. The themes and areas defined were developed following consultations with experts and a mapping of EU policy objectives with the environmental, economic and social outcomes of a food system (similar to what we did in Chapter 4). The environmental dimension comprises five thematic areas, focusing on the complex interdependencies and multifaceted nature of environmental challenges within the food system. It focuses in particular on climate change, pollution and antimicrobials, sustainable resource use, biodiversity and other cross-cutting environmental domains. The economic dimension comprises two key thematic areas that are crucial for a safe, resilient and competitive food system in the EU. They focus on the economic viability of businesses in the food value chain and the development and logistics related to food production and distribution. The social dimension comprises three thematic areas, focusing on fairness and ethics, the food environment and nutrition and health aspects. In addition, governance and resilience are included as cross-cutting thematic areas to cover critical interactions that drive the development of the food system and to provide information on its potential to adapt to sustainability challenges.

Table 5.1 Coverage of food systems dimensions, thematic areas and proposed indicator domains

Sustainability dimension	Thematic area	Indicator Domain
Environmental impacts	Climate change	GHG emissions
	Pollution and antimicrobials	Pollution Antimicrobials
	Sustainable use of resources	Land and soil Water Aquatic living resources Energy
	Biodiversity	Biodiversity conservation and restoration of natural ecosystems Genetic biodiversity of food production systems
	Cross-cutting	Food loss and waste Circular economy Consumption footprint
Economic impacts	Fair economic viability in food value chain	Sectorial growth Market power and business structure Income distribution Price Trade
	Development and logistics	Technology and digitalisation Transport, accessibility and infrastructure
Social impacts	Fair, inclusive and ethical food system	Employment and working conditions Social protection and poverty Animal welfare
	Food environment	Food messaging Food availability Food affordability Properties of food

Sustainability dimension	Thematic area	Indicator Domain
	Nutrition and health	Nutrition and health, sustainable diets Health impacts from diets Food security
Horizontal capacities to respond to food system activities and impacts, and to adapt to challenges of sustainability	Governance	Strategic planning and policies Effective implementation Accountability Shared vision
	Resilience	Preparedness Shock resilience Adaptation Transformation

Source: Acs et al., 2025, Figure 4

These thematic areas, mentioned in the ecological, economic and social dimensions of food system outcomes, are also clearly recognisable in our conceptual figure 2.1 of the food system (see section 2). The cross-cutting themes of governance and resilience are less so. Governance is seen in the literature mainly as a driver of, and not much influenceable by the food system itself; governance is largely shaped in a political and cultural system (Fanzo and Davies, 2021). Resilience is a rather abstract concept that reflects the capacity of a system to respond to shocks or stressors. There is no consensus in the literature on how to measure resilience (e.g. Béné et al., 2018; Bock et al., 2022). The Dashboard team also states that there are major methodological and data challenges to define simple and meaningful metrics to map the state of Governance and Resilience.

The structure of the Monitor does raise some questions. It is striking that economic indicators should lead to a fair economic viability in the food chain, while the term fair seems to belong more to the social domain; after all, the social domain is mainly about the distribution of economic profits (and damage or losses). The thematic domain Development and logistics (and its indicators) also raises some questions: these seem to be more drivers than results of food system outcomes. The place of a number of indicator domains under thematic domains (for example: food security as an indicator domain of the Nutrition and health theme domain) also raises questions that can only be answered by delving deeper into what exactly is hidden as metrics behind the indicator(s).

Quantitative indicators are proposed for each thematic area in the three sustainability dimensions. These indicators in the dashboard, or the data used to calculate them, come from publicly accessible official data sources (such as statistics), or peer-reviewed scientific research. Out of approximately 250 indicators, 179 indicators have been selected (based on a quality assessment framework). A full list of indicators can be found in Acs et al., 2025, Supplementary Material 5. In Table 5.2 below, we show a few examples of indicators that are linked to the (10) thematic areas that are linked to the environmental, economic and social sustainability dimensions also presented in table 5.1 above. Again, it must also be said that it is not always easy to trace the connection between the thematic area and the indicator. For example, for all indicators that are mentioned as contributing to 'Fair economic viability in the food value chain', it is not clear how these address the aspect 'fair'.

Table 5.2 Examples of indicators for measuring environmental, economic and social impacts on food systems

Thematic area	Example indicators
Environmental Impacts	
Climate change	GHG emissions from agriculture; Net GHG emissions from LULUCF sector; Fishing-related CO2 emissions related to fuel used per kilogram of landings (EU)
Pollution and Antimicrobials	Use and risk of chemical pesticides; Use of the more hazardous pesticides; Water quality nitrates in groundwater; Ammonia emissions from agriculture; Sales of antimicrobials for food-producing animals
Sustainable Use of Resources	Share of agricultural area under organic farming; Gross nutrient balance nitrogen; Gross nutrient balance phosphorus; Soil organic carbon in agricultural land; WEI+
Biodiversity	Common farmland birds indicator; Consumption Footprint - Food (biodiversity loss); Grassland butterfly index; Number of genetic resources for food production secured in either medium- or long-term conservation facilities
Cross-cutting	Food loss and waste; Direct agricultural loss attributed to disasters; Circular economy; Consumption Footprint - Food
Economic Impacts	
Fair Economic Viability in Food Value Chain	Value added along the food chain; Labor productivity of the different sectors of the food chain; Gross fixed capital formation in agriculture; Market concentration; Fish landings of EU small-scale fisheries (%); Farmers income in agriculture compared with wages in the rest of the economy; Average salary by sector; Consumer food inflation; Price indices of agricultural inputs; Trade balance; Self-sufficiency rates commodities
Development and Logistics	Rural Next Generation Access broadband coverage; Agricultural training of farm managers; Annual road freight transport by distance class
Social Impacts	
Fair, Inclusive and Ethical Food System	Employment by economic activity; Number of fishers in the EU small-scale fisheries (passive gear); Young farm managers in agriculture; Young fishers; Accidents at work; Share of laying hens by farming method; Organic production of aquaculture products
Food Environment	Number of products under a quality scheme per category and per scheme; Percentage of the population who cannot afford a healthy diet; Affordability of a healthy diet: ratio of cost to total food expenditure; Ratio plant to total protein supply; Supply by food group

Thematic area	Example indicators
Nutrition and Health	Prevalence of exclusive breastfeeding among infants 0-5 months of age; Food consumption (food groups and other dietary factors); Prevalence of overweight and obesity among adults; Prevalence of overweight and obesity among children (aged 6 to 9 years); Prevalence of moderate or severe food insecurity in the population

Source: Acs et al., 2025, Supplementary Material 5.

Looking at the indicators included in the dashboard, there are two observations worth mentioning.

First, the distribution of the indicators across the various themes and domains that the Dashboard distinguishes is rather skewed. The number of indicators is the largest in the environmental themes, namely 99; the economic dimension is covered by 30 indicators and the social dimension by 51. In the environmental sustainability dimension, the number of indicators that can measure the state of sustainability in the domain of land and soil is strikingly large, namely 31. Also in the domain Pollution (12) and Consumer footprint (17) a relatively large number of indicators are suggested as appropriate proxies measuring impacts. In the economic dimension, a considerable number of indicators for measuring sectoral growth, market power and income distribution are included, indicators that all fall within the domain of Fair economic viability. In the social sustainability dimension, a relatively large number of indicators in nutrition and health (8) and health impact of diets (14) are included in the Dashboard.

The large number of indicators per dimension (and thematic area) also means that they are quite diverse and also cover different indicator domains. The question then arises as to how to assess and weigh this diversity in a 'composite' measurement of environmental, economic or social performance.

Second, the sources for the data of the indicators are mainly databases of Eurostat, DG AGRI, DG ENV, EEA, FAO and WHO. Most importantly, JRC has a lot of data at its disposal that can help to determine consumption footprint indicators. The sources are publicly available, and as far as data at JRC are concerned, if not freely available, it should be possible to enter into consultations with JRC about their use.

5.3 The EU Interactive CAP Indicator Dashboard

The Interactive CAP Indicator Dashboard⁸ aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the Common Agricultural Policy's (CAP) performance and its impact on various aspects of agriculture and rural development within the EU. This dashboard, developed and maintained by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development, offers a dynamic tool for stakeholders to monitor and analyse the progress of the CAP towards its specific objectives. It builds upon the established framework of CAP indicators, providing an interactive platform to

⁸ The dashboard can be found here: https://agridata.ec.europa.eu/extensions/DataPortal/cmef_indicators.html. For documentation readers can check: https://agridata.ec.europa.eu/extensions/DataPortal/API_Documentation.html.

explore data, visualize trends, and assess policy effectiveness. The dashboard aligns with the CAP's specific objectives, which are designed to foster a sustainable and competitive agricultural sector, while also supporting rural communities and addressing environmental concerns.

The Interactive CAP Indicator Dashboard offers a structured approach to assessing the CAP's performance, organizing indicators across key dimensions that reflect the policy's objectives. These dimensions are designed to capture the multifaceted impacts of the CAP, enabling users to evaluate its effectiveness in achieving its intended goals. The dashboard provides a user-friendly interface that allows for the exploration of data at various levels of granularity, from EU-wide trends to specific regional or national data. This facilitates a nuanced understanding of the CAP's impact, considering the diverse contexts within the EU. The design of the Dashboard is well-rooted in the CAP's Monitoring and Evaluation Framework (CMEF), ensuring consistency and comparability with existing monitoring systems. Therefore, we use this Dashboard as an important reference for understanding how CAP-specific indicators are utilized and how they relate to the broader food system. This knowledge can give us important insights for our search into the most useful and feasible improvements of our four models in the ACT4CAP27 project in order to be able to perform food system analyses.

The thematic areas and domains of the Interactive CAP Indicator Dashboard are presented in Table 5.3. The themes and areas are derived from the CAP's objectives and priorities, which are aligned with the broader goals of EU policies, including the EGD. The dashboard covers a range of indicators related to the three general objectives of the CAP: (1) fostering a smart, resilient and diversified agricultural sector ensuring food security; (2) bolstering environmental care and climate action and contributing to the environmental- and climate-related objectives of the EU; (3) strengthening the socio-economic fabric of rural areas. These objectives are further specified into eleven specific objectives. The environmental dimension addresses issues such as climate change mitigation, biodiversity conservation, and sustainable resource management. The economic dimension focuses on the viability of agricultural holdings, market stability, and rural income. The social dimension encompasses aspects like rural development, employment, and social inclusion. Cross-cutting objectives related to knowledge, innovation, and digitalization are also included.

Table 5.3 Coverage of CAP dimensions, thematic areas and proposed indicator domains.

(Source: European Commission, Interactive CAP Indicator Dashboard.)

Thematic Indicator	Specific Indicators
Financing the CAP	CAP expenditure over time
	Distribution by main CAP instruments
Farming Income Support	Distribution of income support
	Share in farming income
Jobs and Growth in Rural Areas	GDP per capita in rural areas-
	Incomes in rural areas
	Employment in agriculture
	Poverty rates in rural areas
Market Orientation	EU agri-food trade balance
	Elements of EU competitiveness

Thematic Indicator	Specific Indicators
Adding Value	Value added in agriculture
	Participation in EU quality schemes
	Number of producer organisations
Productivity	Agricultural productivity indicators- Emphasis on rural development support
	EU expenditures devoted to environment- Main land use indicators
Environment and Climate Action	Greenhouse gas emissions from agriculture- Ammonia emissions from agriculture- CAP measures contributing to climate action
Organic Production	Organic farming area
	Number of organic producers
	Specific CAP support for organic production
Water Quality and Availability	Pressures on water quality and quantity- CAP contributions to improved water management
	Soil condition mapping CAP contributions to soil quality preservation
Soil Quality	Biodiversity monitoring CAP contributions to biodiversity protection
	Indicators on plant protection products Use of antimicrobials- Animal welfare measures

These thematic areas, mentioned in the ecological, economic and social dimensions of CAP outcomes, are also clearly recognizable in our conceptual figure 2.1 of the food system (see chapter 2). To better understand how the EU CAP aligns with broader food system impact assessments, table 5.4 maps CAP thematic indicators to relevant food system thematic areas. The CAP dashboard provides insights into various agricultural, environmental, and economic aspects, which can be linked to key sustainability themes such as climate change, resource use, biodiversity, economic viability, and social equity in the food system. By bridging these indicators, policymakers and researchers can evaluate CAP’s contributions to sustainable food systems and identify areas for improvement.

Table 5.4 Mapping the CAP dashboard indicators to the food system impact thematic areas.

Food System Thematic Area	CAP Thematic Indicators	Example Indicators from CAP Dashboard
Environmental Impacts		
Climate Change	Climate Change and Air Quality	Greenhouse gas emissions from agriculture;; CAP measures contributing to climate action

Food System Thematic Area	CAP Thematic Indicators	Example Indicators from CAP Dashboard
Pollution and Antimicrobials	Water Quality and Availability	Pressures on water quality and quantity; CAP contributions to improved water management, Ammonia emissions from agriculture
Sustainable Use of Resources	Organic Production, Soil Quality	Organic farming area; Gross nutrient balance nitrogen and phosphorus; Soil organic carbon in agricultural land
Biodiversity	Biodiversity	Biodiversity monitoring; CAP contributions to biodiversity protection
Cross-cutting		
Food Loss and Waste, Circular Economy	Environment and Climate Action	EU expenditures devoted to environment; Main land use indicators

Food System Thematic Area	CAP Thematic Indicators	Example Indicators from CAP Dashboard
Economic Impacts		
Fair Economic Viability in Food Chain	Market Orientation, Adding Value, Productivity	EU agri-food trade balance; Value added in agriculture; Agricultural productivity indicators; Trade balance; Self-sufficiency rates commodities
Development and Logistics	Jobs and Growth in Rural Areas	Employment in agriculture; Rural Next Generation Access broadband coverage
Social Impacts		
Fair, Inclusive and Ethical Food System	Farming Income Support, Jobs and Growth in Rural Areas	Distribution of income support; Young farm managers in agriculture; Employment in agriculture; Accidents at work

Food System Thematic Area	CAP Thematic Indicators	Example Indicators from CAP Dashboard
Food Environment	Adding Value	Number of products under a quality scheme; Affordability of a healthy diet; Ratio plant to total protein supply
Nutrition and Health	Food and Health Quality Protection	Indicators on plant protection products; Use of antimicrobials; Animal welfare measures; Prevalence of overweight and obesity among adults and children

Quantitative indicators are proposed for each thematic area in the three sustainability dimensions. These indicators in the dashboard, or the data used to calculate them, come from publicly accessible official data sources (such as Eurostat, DG AGRI, and national authorities). A full list of the CAP indicators is available in the Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2021/2115.

Looking at the indicators included in the dashboard, there are two observations worth mentioning.

First, the distribution of the indicators across the various themes and domains that the Dashboard distinguishes reflects the CAP's objectives. There is a balance of indicators across the economic, environmental, and social dimensions, with a specific focus on indicators related to the specific objectives of the CAP.

Second, the main database of the indicators can be found in the Agri-Food Data Portal⁹ The Agri-food Data Portal's Data Explorer, managed by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development, offers a comprehensive suite of agricultural data across the EU. While the platform is robust, certain aspects of data quality, particularly coverage and missing values, requires attention. The portal encompasses diverse datasets, including farm economics, production, prices, and trade statistics. These datasets are sourced from Eurostat, COMEXT, and the Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN). Data is available at both national and EU levels, with temporal coverage extending over multiple years, facilitating trend analysis. Certain datasets, notably FADN, experience a lag in availability. The FADN database also does not represent non-commercial and very small farms, potentially omitting significant segments of the agricultural sector.

In short, the work done to set up the Interactive CAP Indicator Dashboard provides a valuable tool for understanding and monitoring the CAP's performance. It can serve as a key reference for assessing the impact of policy choices on the food system in ACT4CAP27 project.

⁹ <https://agridata.ec.europa.eu/extensions/DashboardIndicators/DataExplorer.html>

5.4 Closing remarks and next steps

Both dashboards described and explained above provide a good starting point for our own quest to strengthen our modelling tools for policy evaluation models. In this we will also progress together with the insights from the Brightspace project in which measurements to quantitatively indicate the save and just operating are also being developed. On which sustainability dimensions can our models be improved and what is needed in terms of data and model structure to strengthen the models in their capacity to measure the impact of policy choices on each of the sustainability dimensions simultaneously? This is the subject of the WP1.3 task, in which we will indicate which model and analytical improvements will be needed to be able to monitor and evaluate the CAP post 2027 on economic, social and environmental outcomes. In WP2 and WP3, work is underway to broaden the thematic coverage of the models to analyse the economic, social and environmental impacts of EU policies (in particular the CAP post 2027, but also other components of the Green Deal) on the EU food system. Both examples of Dashboards indicate that data are available for a large number of indicators from a broad set of themes that influence the state of sustainability in the European food system. It is up to us to investigate how we can use the indicators provided in the EU Food System Monitoring Dashboard and the EU Interactive CAP Indicator Dashboard in the best possible way.

An important question to ask is which sustainability indicators proposed in either dashboard are considered a valuable addition to the result indicators already included in the models. Which criteria are used in this regard? Is there a minimum number of indicators needed to compile a sufficient and robust measurement of the state of affairs of the various economic, social and ecological themes? This requires an objective, ex ante (of conducting food system analyses) selection protocol, for example with inclusion/exclusion criteria (for example in line with the approach followed in Béné et al 2019b). Such a protocol will need to be further elaborated, in the implementation of Task 1.3 of this project. Practical considerations will also play a role in this, such as data availability and the effort required to adapt the model structure to the inclusion of a result indicator. Indeed, the architecture of a model (that is, the causal relationship between driver, activity and outcome) determines the breadth and depth to which models can generate results that provide insight into food system performance in terms of food security, and economic, social and environmental outcomes.

6 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

This report has presented a comprehensive framework for assessing sustainable food system outcomes in the context of EU policies, particularly the EGD and the CAP. By adopting a food systems approach, we have highlighted the complex interactions between economic, social, and environmental dimensions of food production, distribution, and consumption. The analytical framework developed within the ACT4CAP27 project provides a structured methodology to evaluate policy impacts on multiple food system outcomes, ensuring that interventions align with long-term sustainability goals.

Food systems are shaped by a wide range of drivers, including economic market dynamics, technological advancements, social and institutional factors, and biophysical conditions. A key message of this report is that the interactions between these drivers and food system activities generate trade-offs and synergies that must be carefully considered in policy design. While the Green Deal and F2F strategies introduce ambitious targets for sustainability, their implementation requires integrated policy approaches that account for the economic viability of food system actors, the resilience of supply chains, and the accessibility of nutritious diets for all consumers.

Furthermore, our analysis highlights the importance of robust indicators to monitor and evaluate food system performance. The recent development of the EU Food System Dashboard offers a valuable tool for tracking progress across various sustainability dimensions. However, the current state of data availability and modelling capacities still presents limitations in capturing the full scope of food system transformations. In the ACT4CAP27 project, which aims to enhance analytical capacity and tools for supporting Common Agricultural Policies post-2027, we will seek to address these gaps by refining existing modelling tools such as CAPRI, GLOBIOM, MAGNET, and AGMEMOD and incorporating a broader set of indicators to assess the impacts of future policies on EU's food system.

While this report lays the groundwork for an integrated assessment of EU food system policies, further research is required, particularly in relation to Sections 4 and 5. First, a more detailed exploration of the linkages between policy interventions and food system outcomes is needed to ensure that sustainability and resilience targets are met without unintended economic or social consequences. Second, additional work is required to refine and expand the set of indicators used in the EU Food System Dashboard and the Interactive CAP Indicator Dashboard to capture a more comprehensive picture of sustainability transitions and to align with the objectives of the CAP post-2027. This includes improving data collection mechanisms, addressing gaps in socio-economic and environmental indicators, and strengthening the capacity of modelling tools to assess long-term policy impacts. As this is a working document, the findings presented here should be seen as an evolving contribution to the research framework on sustainable food systems. The ACT4CAP27 project will continue to refine its analytical framework and methodologies in collaboration with relevant stakeholders, ensuring that future iterations incorporate the latest developments in policy, data availability, and modelling capabilities. By deepening our understanding of food system dynamics and policy interactions, and by enhancing the analytical tools used to assess policy impacts, this work aims to support evidence-based decision-making and contribute to a just and effective transformation of the EU food system, aligning with Green Deal objectives and the specific goals of the CAP post-2027.

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APPENDIX 1 INDICATORS IN THE COMMON MONITORING AND EVALUATION FRAMEWORK

The Common Monitoring and Evaluation Framework (CMEF) establishes a list of indicators to help assess the performance of the CAP 2014-22 and improve its efficiency. Achievements over the 2014-22 period are presented thematically at the EU and Member State levels. Below is the list of all the indicators included in CMEF¹⁰.

Thematic Indicator	Indicators
Food security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of people at risk of poverty or social exclusion unable to afford a meal with meat, chicken, fish (or vegetarian equivalent) every second day • Share of population reporting difficulties in making ends meet • Share of households with food expenditure below a low-cost food threshold • Share of children (under 16) living in households with food expenditure below a low-cost food threshold • Share of population reporting moderate or severe food insecurity experience • Share of population reporting severe food insecurity experience
Income and productivity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agricultural entrepreneurial income • Agricultural factor income per annual work unit • Labour productivity in agriculture • Total factor productivity in agriculture • Gross value added of the agricultural sector • Gross value added of the food manufacturing sector
Markets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agricultural output price index • Agricultural input price index • Agricultural terms of trade • Producer price indices of agricultural products • Consumer price indices of food and non-alcoholic beverages
Trade	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agricultural trade balance • Food trade balance • Value of EU agricultural exports • Value of EU agricultural imports • Value of EU food exports • Value of EU food imports.
Farm structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Average economic size of farms • Share of family farms • Share of farms by economic size class • Share of agricultural area by farm size class

¹⁰ https://agridata.ec.europa.eu/extensions/DataPortal/cmef_indicators.html and <https://agridata.ec.europa.eu/extensions/DashboardIndicators/DataExplorer.html>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of farms
Generation renewal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Share of young farmers • Share of agricultural area farmed by young farmers
Employment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agricultural employment • Share of female agricultural employment • Employment in the food manufacturing sector
Climate change mitigation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Greenhouse gas emissions from agriculture • Greenhouse gas intensity of agriculture • Agricultural soil carbon change.
Climate change adaptation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agricultural area under irrigation • Water exploitation index for agriculture • Agricultural losses due to climatic events.
Environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ammonia emissions from agriculture • Nitrate in groundwater • Sales of pesticides • Agricultural land under organic farming • Share of agricultural land under High Nature Value farming • Farmland bird index.
Animal welfare	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of antimicrobial veterinary medicinal products in food-producing animals • Animal welfare indicators.
Rural areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Population density in rural areas • Risk of poverty or social exclusion in rural areas • Broadband coverage in rural areas.
Innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public expenditure on agricultural research and development • Private expenditure on agricultural research and development • Share of farms using digital technologies.

<https://act4cap27.eu>

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